

MAIN FEATURES OF JOURNALISTIC TEXT

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ABSTRACT

The article invites the reader to pay attention to the main features of the journalistic text. As a result, it will retain its importance in the conditions of the emergence of a competitive environment for mass media in the modern information space. Considering the journalistic text as an operational knowledge necessary for reliable orientation to the ever-changing reality for man and society, the author emphasizes its differences from scientific knowledge, opinions, and texts of social networks. This reveals the role of professional journalism in the media system and its competitive advantages over "consumer content" creators.

According to a number of researchers, social the most important of the forms of existence of the speech environment and one of the means of reflection of socio-cultural reality are means of mass communication. They are now speakers in their conversation Information exchange is the most important in social existence plays the role of sources. V.G. According to Kostomarov, all mass media texts The question of "holding the audience" for is a coin. Constant communication with the audience.

Active cooperation, important and interesting information addition, limited to the narrow environment of communication without remaining, all the time influencing the attention of the audience is the simplest method of weighing. At its discretion, the addressee of the media "directly" writes to the journalist enters into a dialogue with . With the addressee mutual personal relations of the addressee - sympathy, there is harmony, dispute, conflict, etc.

Journalistic text is addressed to the audience and makes its own judgment is a conductive source of energy; power over him subject author of the text, editor, presenter the audience listening to this text is to influence are optional objects. One of the tasks of the journalistic text author is is to establish a close relationship with the addressee and interest him. The basis for journalistic texts is oriented towards the addressee was the task of finding a way for a future conversation with him remains. To find a solution to this task, journalist with the organizers of communicative competence finding a way to "work in cooperation", speaking and has the knowledge of "self-organization" of speech texts required to be. Social psychology and sociolinguistic perspectives journalistic text is evaluated as follows:

- informative and clear acceptance by a person or group of people media designed to transmit classified information as rot;

- to the thoughts and behavior of a person or a group of people information that can be influenced, the style of speech bi and as a view. A journalist imagines himself with a certain role, a certain task.

The oil identifies with the subject and to that subject does not know his interest and position lubricates. A journalist creates a unique reality, this scientific description of real events and other journalistic and non-journalistic organizations is fundamentally different from twists.

The main goal of journalism is actual evaluation of the personality and inculcating this evaluation in the public mind. The scope of journalists' activity is the scope of relevance. His task (function) - clear current events to the public mind based on the absorption of evaluations. The general functional effectiveness of the journalistic text level of satisfaction of audience interest and information depends on the correct dosage of This is journalism work, its unique and professional characteristics determines public importance. Journal of text creation what is important for the list is the misinterpretation of information tation, finding the specified psychological barriers and having the knowledge to eliminate them. A journalist turns thoughts into meaning while creating a text.

The author can only successfully communicate to the necessary understanding. Used rules of everyday speech leading to nication can be achieved without Thus journalistic texts to find specific procedures in the formation of text. How successful is the internal explicit logic of s creating the necessary conditions for communication can be known to lead to. It should be noted that universality in journalism not always a solution to all problems. Exactly if a specific goal needs to be achieved, professional you have to rely on guts. Data collection, sources processing, thinking about the essence of the text and interpreting it from a journalist in weighing all genres and forms universality, moreover, orientation to a specific field is required will be done.

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